

A New Unknown Type of Electromagnetic Rays has been Discovered

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Z-Rays

It seems that a new kind of waves do exist in the nature too unknown for the mankind still in addition to already known to us types of electromagnetic waves. New type of the waves has been named by a discoverer the z-rays. The z-rays can be met everywhere - representatives of the human kingdom (i.e. humans), representatives of the animal kingdom (i.e. animals), representatives of the mineral kingdom (e. g. mountains and hills, stones and buildings built by humans etc.), representatives of the plants' kingdom (e. g. trees, flowers, other plants etc.), even planets, planetary moons, stars, also galaxies have individual aureolas which consist of the z-rays' energy. Our naked eyes are unable to detect z-rays under ordinary conditions because the rays' photometric energy quantity tends to zero. If the hypothesis on the z-rays is true, then it can lead to making several new scientific conclusions. In compliance with one of them Mr. A.Einstein's equation on Energy and mass $E = mc^2$ becomes only a special case of a more encompassing Energy equation: where the last summand is the sum-total of energies of invisible (for naked human eyes) parts of the body (or of the field.)An author of the discovery on the z-rays says that he had performed research work that had lasted decades prior to making the conclusion on the z-waves presence in the nature.

$$E = mc^2 + \sum E_{z_i},$$

A Brief Foreword

In compliance with the modern theory of electromagnetic field there are following types of electromagnetic waves: radio-, micro-, infrared-, visual-, ultraviolet-, x-, gamma rays. These rays are met universally. But in the past mankind didn't know about existence of many of them until times of their discovery, e.g. X-rays. Now, too, we can be unaware as to existence of other types of rays or physical waves still unknown to us. It seems there are other kinds of rays in the nature. At least one more kind of them. My research that has been conducted during the last 37 years lets me make the statement.

A New Ray

From the childhood years I've seen many times in my life photography related things and phenomena. Photos of humans, nature objects and various other things were in many cases

original sources of information and interest for me. Watching and contemplating on some of them and analyzing via special method structures of the objects in photos I've detected a presence of a new, unknown type of waves being inseparably present always there in photos together with easily seen by human eyes ordinary pictures of the objects.

Having analyzed my many years-long watchings several years before I did come to a conclusion on existence in the Universe of a one more kind of rays or waves (apart from the known to us ones.) The detected newly kind of waves (rays) is of completely other nature and frequency than those already known to mankind types of electromagnetic waves. Let me call it the z-rays (Wilhelm Conrad Röntgen had called X-ray discovered by him himself ray, so that one must be called in the aforesaid way I did think, because next letters of the Latin alphabet are y, z.)

Where is the proof? Let me explain: if look at photos of humans, animals or various other objects (e.g. buildings, trees, mountain peaks etc.) you can see there in the photos ordinary pictures of corresponding objects as they usually are. If look at taken photos of humans, animals or various other objects (e.g. buildings, trees, mountain peaks etc.) using my original method one can see there in the photos a faint light glowing around aforesaid humans', animals' or various other objects' bodies. As a result of use of the aforesaid my method that light will be visible at the abovementioned bodies' external boundaries along entire perimeter lines of the bodies.

Now let's look at Figures 1 (you can find the photo at www.philipchudy.com), 2, 3, and 1A, 2A, 3A given below. The Figures 1, 2, 3 are ordinary photos of ordinary objects. The corresponding Figures 1A, 2A, 3A are the same photos of the same ordinary objects. But in the latter photos in a clearer way one can see presence of an unusual glowing light located close to and alongside the external border-lines of the aforesaid objects' bodies. In Figures 1B, 2B, 3B the abovementioned 'glowing light' has been encircled by red lines (i.e. the author of these lines tried a bit to process the photos of Figures 1, 2, 3 in compliance with a method devised by him himself in order to make clearer presence of z-rays. The results of the attempt are given below as Figures 1A, 2A, 3A and Figures 1B, 2B, 3B.)

Figure 1: A photo of a man.

Figure: 1A.

Figure: 1B.

Figure 2: A photo of a mountain.

Figure: 2A.

Figure: 2B.

Figure 3: A photo of wild mustangs.

Figure: 3A.

Figure: 3B.

Some people could argue that the glowing light present in those encircled by the red paint parts of the photos given above are nothing but a result of special photographic effects that usually take place when taking photos, therefore there are not any real presence of any unusual types of light – i.e. they could argue that ‘z-rays’ phenomenon can’t exist in the nature. But I dare say that the ‘z-rays’ do exist. Z-rays are of an extremely subtle nature as my experiments have shown. Therefore it’s very difficult to detect them by naked human eyes (if train human eyes via a special method positive results might be obtained regarding seeing z-rays after many months or years of a persistent training. But there is no 100% guarantee that everyone will attain a positive result in this endeavor, because potential powers of humans’ corresponding faculties differ.) A naked human eye is unable to detect z-rays under ordinary conditions because the rays’ radiometric and photometric energy quantities differ – the photometric energy quantity tends to zero and at the same time the radiometric energy quantity does not - i.e. though z-rays do exist they are invisible to naked human eyes like X-rays, gamma rays etc.:

$$K = \Phi_z / \Phi_s \approx 0,$$

because $\Phi_z \approx 0$ though $\Phi_s \neq 0$,

where

K is the luminous efficacy of the z- rays;

Φ_z is the luminous flux of the z- rays;

Φ_s is the radiant flux of the z- rays.

Presence of certain conditions must be secured in order to enable a human eye to clearly see these differences during the use of my method. But it can be more detailedly explained during the face-to-faces meeting or face-to-faces conversation via Internet, if some research organization or university offers me cooperation or co-working as to conducting deeper studies and research of properties of z-rays (waves.)

Conclusion

In addition to known electromagnetic spectrum waves we must take into account existence and influence of z-rays too when considering and studying various phenomena, including those related to events taking place in the nature or humans’ lives.

One thing that ought to be mentioned here is a universality of existence of z-rays. I’ve noticed - when examining - its presence not only around human beings, animals, buildings and other earthly objects but also around celestial objects such as planets, planetary moons as well as galaxies (here I’d like to mention that proving the existence of z-rays around intensively emitting electromagnetic waves shining objects of the Nature like stars and galaxies might require a use of special methods of measurement. Because the emission of the waves by the stars and galaxies can complicate the measurement process. E.g. skeptics might argue that the Galactic Halo of our galaxy is nothing but only stars and other physical objects - located there in the region of the Universe called by us the Galactic Halo – (like interstellar dust particles reflecting a stellar light belonging to the visible light range of the electromagnetic waves spectrum etc.) and their visible light.) Recognition of existence of Z-rays and taking it into account would make a considerable contribution to further progress of many branches of science, including medicine, physics, chemistry, biology, biophysics, psychology (especially subfields of the latter connected with physiology), social sciences, astronomy, philosophy etc.

It must be noted that taking into account the factor of z-rays might be of a special use when examining condition of humans’ organisms for medical purposes (let’s remember a huge positive role that devices using X-rays play today in medicine – a potential medical application of this new kind of waves served as an impulse for me as to making faster a publication of the news on the z-rays’ discovery.)

It seems that some people - who had lived many centuries before - knew the existence of the x-rays. For example, certain ancient times’ and the Middle Ages’ sculptors and painters had depicted some well-known saints with halos shining around their bodies, especially heads. Some examples of the kind of the art pieces are given below (Fig.4, Fig.5, Fig.6. You can find the original source of information on the art pieces.

Figure 4: Apollo with a radiant halo in a Roman floor mosaic (late 2nd century, El Djem, Tunisia).

Figure 5: Standing Buddha with a halo, 1st–2nd century AD (or earlier), Greco-Buddhist art of Gandhara.

Figure 6: The Salvator Mundi, 1570, by Titian.

(A one more interesting idea that can have indirect but meaningful relation to a describing how we may be unaware of presence of things that can exist beyond the borderlines of reach of our five senses. An X-ray photo of a human hand has been given beneath taken by Mr. Wilhelm Roentgen himself during the process of discovery of X-rays (Fig. 7.) An accurate study of the photo will show us that visible to ordinary naked

human eyes the hand's parts consisting of flesh can't be seen in the photo (The photo can serve as a brilliant example of how a hypothetical living being seeing the external world within the range of X-rays' part of electromagnetic waves' spectrum would see a picture of objects belonging to surrounding him/her environment.) But in reality the hand's parts consisting of flesh exist and all we know it. In the same way we might be – and are in reality I suppose - unable to see by our naked eyes the matter consisting of z-rays or z-waves, though the rays and matter do exist really.

As well we don't see using our naked eyes the infrared radiation emitting from a human body, though it really exists (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9).

Figure 7: An X-ray photo of a human hand taken by Mr. Wilhelm Conrad Röntgen.

Figure 8: A human's thermal image photo taken in infrared.

Figure 9: The depicted in Fig. 8 human's ordinary photograph (The plastic bag is mostly transparent to long-wavelength infrared).

Using our naked eyes we are unable to see the infrared radiation emitting from a human body, though it really exists (Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infrared>.) Many questions appear if recognize that z-rays are present in the Universe: Why z-waves can be detected everywhere where we see material objects (as inseparable parts of the latter)? Does it mean that every material object has a body(-ies)-copy(-ies) consisting of z-waves' energy or emitting the latter? Perhaps all the Universe –

and every atom in it – has a copy(-ies) consisting of z-waves' energy? If it is so, then it will mean that a parallel Universe does exist there around us. However, I'd like to mention that this statement on a parallel Universe is only a hypothesis. Perhaps a proto-matter exists there in the Nature – i.e. a matter from which all known and unknown still to us types of matter have been originated? If the proto-matter exists then could z-rays lead us to its discovery?)

I think it is possible that there are other waves existing in the Universe also apart from (known to us electromagnetic waves and) z-rays, which nature and properties we don't know still. They might have quite different energetical-spectral-domains-of-dwelling (in the spectrum of electromagnetic waves) and physical characteristics compared with z-rays' ones. I call them the pan-z-rays (the prefix "pan-" has been borrowed from Ancient Greek παν- (pan-), combining form of πᾶς (pâs, "all, every".))

We can make several conclusions if all the aforesaid is true. In compliance with one of them Mr. Einstein's equation on Energy and mass becomes only a special case of a more encompassing Energy equation: is the sum-total of energies of invisible (for naked human eyes) parts of the body (or of the field.) And in special cases that can take place in the nature these invisible (for naked human eyes) parts of the body (or of the field) can play a role of sources of the z- rays and the pan-z-rays emitted by the body (or of the field.)

$$E = mc^2$$

$$E = mc^2 + \sum E_{z_i},$$

where

- E is the total Energy of a body (or of a field);
- m is the mass of the physical (visible) part of the body (or of the field);
- c is the speed of light; and the last summand

$$\sum E_{z_i}$$

In the article given above not all discovered properties of z-rays were disclosed. Because it would require more writing space... I'm open for co-working with research organizations and universities as to performing further research activities aimed at studying other unknown aspects and properties of the above-

said z-rays (I'd like to mention here that in compliance with the corporate philosophy of the Ultranova Technologies LLC. (i.e. lead by me company), the company can't take part in activities related to preparation and production of any kind of weaponry – including weapons of mass destruction – as well as alcoholic beverages, tobaccos, drugs, items of gambling industry, because the goods and services might harm humans' lives or make them victims of various types of negative psycho-physiological dependencies. Therefore I can't include into the list of my potential partners as to conducting the researches on z-rays organizations which activities are performed fully or mainly in spheres of preparation and production of aforesaid goods and services.

References

1. Panchbhai AS. Wilhelm Conrad Rontgen and the discovery of X-rays: Revisited after centennial. *Journal of Indian academy of oral medicine and radiology*. 2015 ;27(1):90.
2. Yuan W, Zhang C, Ling Z, Zhao D, Wang W, Chen Y, Lu F, Zhang SN, Cui W. Einstein Probe: a lobster-eye telescope for monitoring the x-ray sky. In *Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2018: Ultraviolet to Gamma Ray 2018* (Vol. 10699, p. 1069925). International Society for Optics and Photonics.
3. Criss JW, Birks LS. Calculation methods for fluorescent x-ray spectrometry. Empirical coefficients versus fundamental parameters. *Analytical Chemistry*. 1968 ;40(7):1080-6.
4. Steinberg BZ, Leviatan Y. On the use of wavelet expansions in the method of moments (EM scattering). *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*. 1993 ;41(5):610-9.
5. Bruning J, Lo Y. Multiple scattering of EM waves by spheres part I-- Multipole expansion and ray-optical solutions. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*. 1971 ;19(3):378-90.
6. Amendolia SR, Arik M, Badelek B, Batignani G, Beck GA, Bedeschi F, Bellamy EH, Bertolucci E, Bettoni D, Bilokon H, Bologna G. A measurement of the space-like pion electromagnetic form factor. *Nuclear Physics B*. 1986 ;277:168-96.
7. Schaubert D, Wilton D, Glisson A. A tetrahedral modeling method for electromagnetic scattering by arbitrarily shaped inhomogeneous dielectric bodies. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*. 1984 ;32(1):77-85.
8. Dawid AP, Skene AM. Maximum likelihood estimation of observer error-rates using the EM algorithm. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C (Applied Statistics)*. 1979 ;28(1):20-8.
9. Schatz GC, Van Duyne RP. Electromagnetic mechanism of surface-enhanced spectroscopy. *Handbook of vibrational spectroscopy*. 2002;1:759-74.